

1 Unglazed Solar Thermal 2 Systems for Building 3 Integration, coupled with 4 District Heating Systems. 5 Conceptual Definition, Cost 6 and Performance Assessment

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13 **Abstract**

14 *In this paper, the energy performance of a solar thermal (ST) façade system is studied in*
15 *relation to its connection to a district heating system. This concept allows for the direct use of*
16 *ST heat in the building, while taking profit from the network for delivery/selling of excess heat*
17 *and purchase of heat during periods of underproduction. The use of unglazed collectors for*
18 *low-intrusive architectural interaction in façades is discussed.*

19 *Studies are carried out on the heat production of the system and its capacity to cope with local*
20 *demands. Economic studies are carried out in order to balance the investment and operational*
21 *costs/profits of the system.*

22 **Keywords**

23 solar systems, thermal energy, building integration, energy systems.

24

25 **1 Introduction**

26 In developed countries, there is a clear need, and political impulse, to achieve an energetic
27 transition from fossil fuels to renewable sources. Within renewable energy sources, the
28 potential of solar power and associated technologies is well known. In particular, solar thermal
29 systems are a proven renewable heating technology. Although the exergy of this energy source
30 is quite low, the potential of solar energy is still one of the greatest on the planet (Ehsanul,
31 Kumar, Kumar, Adelodun, & Kim, 2018).

32 In this context, solar energy must be one of the main pillars of a renewable energy strategy. A
33 clear example of the drive towards this transition is the minimum solar contribution required by
34 national building codes in developed countries, such as the Spanish CTE (2013).

35 In most traditional heating system designs, Solar Thermal (ST) systems are sized to meet only
36 a fraction of the entire demand for thermal energy. Solar production and heat loads in buildings
37 have daily and seasonal variations due to transient and variable weather conditions. In most
38 climates, space heating (SH) load is interrupted in summer periods, but domestic hot water
39 (DHW) loads are stable all year round. In winter, the available ST heat is not sufficient to cover
40 heat loads in buildings, while in summer, solar heat production clearly exceeds the demand of
41 the building. ST systems are commonly sized not to exceed heat loads over the spring-autumn
42 period.

43 Most ST systems are incorporated in roofs. In order to meet the increased requirements for ST
44 installation, larger surfaces will need to be activated for ST installations. For this, building
45 façades need to be considered as candidate areas due to their large available surface,
46 although challenges of overshadowing in high urban building densities must still be resolved.

47 With the steady incorporation of nZEB (nearly Zero Energy Buildings) in cities, relevant
48 reductions in heat loads can be foreseen in the near future. The utilisation of renewable
49 energies in these same buildings will reach a point where the directionality in the production-
50 consumption role will be altered. The increase in ST installation with the reduction of heat loads
51 in buildings modifies traditional ST sizing criteria. As a result, excess heat may be available
52 from these ST systems. In this paper, the connection to district heating (DH) is explored in
53 order to allow this excess production to be used in adjacent buildings.

54 DH systems are one of the most efficient ways to cover heat loads in urban areas.
55 Traditionally, DH systems have been based on large boilers or CHP (combined heat & power)
56 systems. Nowadays, it is increasingly common to find DH networks that incorporate distributed
57 energy sources (Monsalvete Álvarez de Urbarrí, Eicker, & Robinson, 2017), commonly with
58 lower exergy in comparison with traditional high temperature power plants.

59 This includes the exploitation of industrial waste heat and solar thermal systems, among
60 others. All this results in a reduction of fossil fuel dependence and contributes to a de-
61 carbonised environment.

62 Heat losses in the DH system are proportional to the temperature gradient between supply
63 temperature and environment temperature. With lower operational temperatures and
64 distributed energy sources, there is a substantial improvement in system performance.

65 In this paper, the potentialities, constraints, and performance levels of façade-integrated solar
66 thermal systems coupled with low temperature district heating (LTDH) are studied, comprising
67 their thermal and economic performance. The techno-economic viability of unglazed façade-
68 integrated solar thermal systems when combined with low temperature district heating
69 systems.

70 1.1 Unglazed Solar thermal collectors

71 In general, ST systems are composed of solar thermal collectors, where a heat transfer fluid is
72 circulated in a pressurised circuit. Solar heat is absorbed and transferred to the fluid, resulting
73 in an increment of the temperature. Depending on external conditions and collectors`
74 characteristics, the performance of each collector is different. Their performance definition is
75 described in detail in (Duffie and Beckman, 1980).

76 Inlet fluid parameter, °K; T_m equals mean collector fluid temperature; T_a equals ambient temperature.

77 FIG 1. Collector efficiency vs $(T_m - T_a)$. $G_T = 800W/m^2$. Source: Stickney, B. & Soifer, B, (2009).

78 Fig. 1 shows that with a low temperature difference, unglazed collectors present better
79 efficiency levels than other systems. The possibility to incorporate unglazed systems in
80 buildings has been studied in diverse investigations such as (A. Giovanardi, 2016) but only a
81 few companies propose integration into the façade, and the technology is still under-exploited.

82 1.2 Architectural Integration of ST systems

83 Building integration of ST systems has been historically limited due to the need to
84 accommodate glazed areas and tubular assemblies in the architectural composition of
85 buildings. Despite this, smart but marginal integration solutions for vacuum tubes have been
86 achieved in balconies or transparent areas (O'Hegarty, Kinnane, and McCormack, 2016)

87 As for the unglazed collectors, the method for their integration in façades is explained in (Garay
88 Martinez, R., Arregi Goikolea, B., Bonnamy, P. & Lopez, J., 2017). Having no glass or tubular
89 covers, the unglazed collectors are the only ones that can be integrated without modifying the
90 aesthetics of the building. Specifically, the unglazed solar collector enables varied forms
91 (shape, size, and typology) and materials (colour, texture, transparency etc.).

92 In broad terms, it must be considered that façades are the prominent image of the building. In
93 the selection of ST technologies and their integration with solar thermal façades (STF), this
94 aspect needs to be taken into account. The existence of a wide range of architectural façades
95 requires delivery of a wide range of STF products, to ensure freedom of design intent. In

96 (Garay Martinez, Arregi Goikolea, Bonnamy, and Lopez, 2017), an experimental study is
97 performed on unglazed ST collectors and their potential to deliver heat to HVAC systems in
98 buildings. In this work, it is identified that façades are the biggest area on to which collectors
99 can be installed, and that unglazed collectors are one of the most sensible alternatives to
100 achieve ST production and architectural integration.

101 1.3 ST connection to DH networks

102 With the trend to incorporate decentralised and decarbonised heat, ST is an increasingly
103 common alternative heat source being incorporated in DH. There are two integration
104 alternatives for ST in DH: centralised and distributed ST systems. To date, most ST
105 installations have consisted of centralised ST plants outside cities. This paper explores the
106 possibility to integrate distributed ST systems in buildings, by means of their integration in
107 building façades. This allows for the moving of energy sources closer to consumption points to
108 reduce the transmission losses associated with the aforementioned centralised plant. DH
109 connection of ST systems can be performed in different ways, with different functionalities.
110 (Sanchez Zabala and Garay Martinez, 2017) describe several types of connections. FIG 2.
111 shows different types of ST integration schemes into a DH network.

112

113 FIG 2. ST integration into DH networks. A. ST & DH in parallel. B. Delivery of excess heat to DH. C. Hybrid system
114 without storage (Sanchez Zabala & Garay Martinez, 2017)

115 This paper explores a direct ST and DH connection to central HVAC manifolds in building,
116 allowing bi-directional heat transfer to the DH. In this concept, local storage is avoided.

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118 2 Methodology

119 In this paper, simulations are performed in order to assess the technical and economic viability
120 of unglazed ST systems connected to DH networks in order to deliver decarbonised heat within
121 reasonable economic metrics.

122 For this purpose, simulation studies are performed for a multi-storey building in the region of
123 Bordeaux (France). According to the Koppen-Geiger climate definition, described by (Kottek,
124 M., Grieser, J., Beck, C., Rudolph, B., & Rubel, F., 2006), Bordeaux is classified as having a
125 C_{fb} climate, which covers most climates in Western Europe, from the north of Spain to central
126 EU latitudes such as UK, The Netherlands, etc... For this reason, Bordeaux is considered to be
127 a representative location for West-EU climates.

128 The heat load, for DHW and space heating is calculated by means of dynamic simulation
129 methods with an hourly resolution. Heat production of a south-oriented ST façade is simulated
130 for the same climate with the same resolution.

131 The economic viability of DH-connected ST systems is evaluated by means of a comparative
132 study against fossil-fuel alternatives. Various ST connection & heat pricing schemes are
133 studied.

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135 *FIG 3. Methodology description*

136 2.1 Heat Load Modelling

137 The first step in this study is developing the building model and defining its main
138 characteristics, depending on which the heat loads vary considerably. The selected case study
139 comprises a 5-storey building, with a façade surface area of 1250 m². In Fig. 4, a general view
140 of the building and its basic connection scheme to DH is shown. The U-value of the walls is 0.8

141 W/m². The window-to-wall ratio is 40% with a U-value of 1.4 W/m². Fig. 4 shows general
142 prototypes for ST integration in the building and its connection to DH substation.

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145 *FIG 4. 3D model of the building geometry & ST system on the south façade (left); Connection scheme within the*
146 *collector field and connection to DH (right)*

147 DHW heat load has been calculated according to (Código Técnico de la Edificación [Technical
148 Building Code] , 2013), considering a total floor area of 5000m² divided in 80m² apartments
149 inhabited by families comprising 3 people. According to the calculation procedure, 22 litres of
150 DHW (60°C) are consumed per person per day.

151 For SH, a pseudo dynamic calculation has been used, with a self-developed procedure that is
152 compliant with UNE-EN ISO 13790:2011.

153 2.2 Modelling of the Unglazed ST System

154 For the modelling of the ST façade, a self-developed model in the software R has been used
155 for thermal calculations. This software tool allows big databases to be worked with as vectors,
156 thereby reducing calculation times. Within this model, specific collector Energie Solaire
157 Kollektor AS (2012) data has been used in order to calculate efficiency and other parameters
158 used in the model.

159 As for the working temperatures, the inlet temperature has been fixed in order to be the same
160 as the DH return line temperature (± 30 °C) and the outlet temperature from the collector field
161 has been set according to each of the simulation cases, which are further defined later in the
162 text. Moreover, load losses have been estimated to be 10%.

163 2.3 Considerations for Economic Metrics

164 The economic assessment is based on general economic metrics which can be found in
165 general purpose economic literature such as (Harris, 2018). For their calculation, the
166 investment necessary for the installation and exploitation of each technology has been
167 calculated, leading to the calculation of the yearly revenues and operational costs. This will
168 include the consumption of primary energy sources and the heat purchase and delivery. As it is

169 a theoretical study, the maintenance costs have been avoided for being much lower in
170 comparison with other cash flows.

171 Specifically, the metrics used for this economic assessment are as follows: return on
172 investment (ROI), which is the time taken to recover the investment; cash flow, the net amount
173 of cash moving in and out of each technology; and net present value (NPV), which is the
174 difference between the present value of cash inflows and the present value of cash outflows
175 over a period of time.

176 3 Thermal Performance of Unglazed ST System

177 A ST collector system is studied in a high-rise building. This collector field comprises 240m² of
178 south-oriented unglazed ST. The field is arranged in 20 parallel circuits, comprising 6 collectors
179 in a serial arrangement, with each collector covering an area of 2m². Data relating to the
180 specific collector used for this installation can be found in Energie Solaire Kollektor AS (2012).

181 In general, collectors achieve better efficiency when the temperature difference between the
182 collector (average) and environment is low. In order to limit the average in the solar field, a
183 sensitivity analysis is carried out to ensure that the inlet-outlet temperature difference is limited
184 to 10 °C. That temperature difference is defined by the difference between the average
185 temperature in the collector battery and the ambient temperature. This results in the
186 aforementioned configuration.

187 In an isolated system, the service temperature needs to be met by solar thermal collectors. In
188 these systems, it is common to use the lowest possible service temperature to increase the
189 overall performance of ST. In the case of considering ST systems coupled with DH, there is no
190 need to configure ST systems to raise fluid temperature to the overall flow temperature in the
191 DH network. There is a minimum temperature difference (normally 3-5°C) that the system must
192 achieve before it is worth activating the pumps to circulate the fluid. If the heat output is
193 delivered in the return pipe of the DH, greater performance is achieved due to the lower service
194 temperature compared to insulated ST systems. In Fig. 5, the results from the simulation of
195 unglazed ST when reacting to different situations are shown.

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FIG 5. Collector in serial arrangement performance for different situations

198 Depending on the service temperature required, the number of collectors arranged in series
 199 increases, so that the surface needed increases proportionally. Taking into account the fact
 200 that the inlet-outlet temperature difference is limited, the number of collectors is also limited.

201 Nowadays, LTDH (low temperature district heating) is considered as an alternative to
 202 conventional DH, and the working temperatures of this system are much lower, reducing heat
 203 losses in supply temperatures. In this case, the best solution for installing integrated ST is to
 204 install the ST system to the return pipe of LTDH system.

205 4 Results

206 4.1 Heat Production

207 Solar production is simulated for the climate of Bordeaux for various operational conditions.
 208 These conditions consider various inlet temperatures, among which low temperatures are
 209 incorporated and used in line with LTDH. Temperatures in the range of 50-60°C are
 210 representative of flow temperatures, while temperatures of 20-30°C are representative of DH
 211 return lines. In Fig. 6, the total heat production of a solar unglazed collector (Energie Solaire
 212 Kollektor AS, 2012) and the total efficiency defined by the production, divided by the total solar
 213 radiation, are shown. The bar plot refers to the total solar production by the unglazed collector;
 214 the lines refer to the total efficiency. The results indicate that better results are achieved for the
 215 cases in which the inlet-outlet temperature difference is limited to 10°C, no matter what the inlet
 216 temperature is.

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FIG 6. Solar production and total solar efficiency for different inlet temperatures

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Temperature differences in the range of 10°C can be used to inject heat to the return line of the

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DH system.

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4.2 Economic viability

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The economical assessment of DH connected ST system is studied against several benchmark

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cases (natural gas boilers, electric heaters etc.). Investment and operational costs are

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calculated and the economic performance of the system is calculated over the service life of

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the system.

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Investment and operational costs have been calculated for the cases under review. Investment

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costs cover the equipment and installation costs of each system. Representative HVAC

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systems for multi-storey buildings have been used and their cost normalised per kW. Data has

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been taken from (Precio centro Guadalajara, 2018) and from (Tarifa de precios solar térmica

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Salvador Escoda, 2018).

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Table 1: Installation cost per unit of power for different technologies

Technology	Material installation costs (€/kW)
Natural gas boiler	85
Joule heater	5
Ground source heat pump	692
Unglazed collector without DH	915
Unglazed collector with DH	608

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239 In Table 2, the breakdown of the investment costs is presented.

240 Table 2: Cost estimation for ST installation. Source: Tarifa de precios solar térmica Salvador Escoda [Salvador Escoda
241 solar thermal price list] (2018).
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Concept	Unitary cost (€/unit)	Quantity	Total €
Solar Collector RK // ALPIN RKM 2001 2m ²	305	120	36630 €
Support assembly for façades // SFV-AR	120	120	14400 €
Valves and other installation materials	---	---	4041 €
Workforce costs	---	---	7251€
Total	---	---	62023 €

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252 Operational costs incorporate the primary energy consumed by heating systems. The cost of
253 primary energy sources are shown in Table 3.

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Table 3: Prices for primary sources (2016)

Primary energy	Price (€/kWh)
Natural gas	0.05
Electricity	0.14
ST	0
DH heat (UNE-EN ISO 13790:2011)	0.0685
Heat purchase (estimated 70% of DH heat cost) (UNE-EN ISO 13790:2011)	0.04795

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258 The cost of DH has been obtained from the commercial price of heat in the DH network in
259 Paris, specifically; data has been obtained from (Tarifs de Vente CPCU, 2016), which is one of
260 the largest networks in EU. As for the DH cases, it has been assumed that the heat produced
261 by ST system could be sold to DH network at two price points: 100% of heat price produced in
262 DH and 70% of the heat price produced in DH. This is simply a consideration in order to
263 simulate an ideal case, as well as a more realistic one.

264 Investment and operational costs of all alternative systems studied are recorded in Fig. 7.

265

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FIG 7. Initial investment and operational costs for each technology

267 The case of the ST system coupled with DH has negative operational costs. For the calculation
 268 of such operational costs, it has been considered that all of the heat demand from the building
 269 is obtained from the DH supply line and the heat produced by the ST is, in its entirety, sold to
 270 DH. In this way, general data used for these calculations is recorded in Table 4.

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Table 4: Operational cost overview

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Heat load (SH+DHW) (kWh/year)	424040
Solar production (kWh/year)	138196
Income from ST 70% (€/year)	9466
Income from ST 100% (€/year)	6626

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274 It is clearly seen that both ST systems, with and without the DH network, require a larger initial
 275 investment than typical natural gas boilers or electrical heaters. If a DH network is available,
 276 the possibility to deliver excess heat to the DH offsets the cost of heat purchased in winter
 277 periods. This results in negative operational costs. The income from heat sold to DH is higher
 278 than the cost of heat purchases from the DH network.

279 The evolution of the cumulative cost of each of the technologies is shown in Fig. 8. Natural gas
 280 boilers have been taken as a reference, thus, the accumulated differential cost against this
 281 technology is provided. The case of Joule heating has been removed due to its clearly anti-

282 economic performance and in order to see the cost comparison in more detail. For the
 283 purposes of calculation in Fig. 8, the interest rate has not been considered.

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286 *FIG 8. Cost evolution for different technologies, with Gas boiler as reference*

287 From Fig. 8, it is resolved that ST connected to DH return line shows better economic
 288 performance than conventional gas boilers when the second year has passed.

289 Table 5 presents the return of investment (ROI) for DH-connected ST façades for various
 290 interest rates. Interest rates of 5% and 10% are considered.

291 *Table 5: Return of Investment for cases where DH is installed (years)*
 292

	ST to DH return 100%	ST to DH 70%
ROI (i = 5%)	5.554	6.858
ROI (i = 10%)	5.097	5.853

293

294 5 Discussion

295 In this work the possibility to incorporate unglazed solar thermal collectors in the context of DH
 296 is studied.

297 The economic metrics of the presented case study show good feasibility, with ROIs in the
 298 range of 5-6 years. In this context, it is crucial to understand that heat purchase agreements
 299 need to be defined at a DH scale. These agreements substantially affect the economic metrics.

300 In the presented study, the payback period is reduced by 1-2 years when heat purchase price
301 is reduced to 70%.

302 Considering the data presented in Fig. 8, the connection to DH substantially improves the
303 economic metrics of the ST systems, with payback periods reduced from 6-7 years to ~2 years.

304 Although the ST collector field incorporates relevant capital costs for the installation of the ST
305 system, the connection to the DH avoids the need for large heat production systems to be
306 installed for back-up, through reducing investments in auxiliaries, and reducing operational
307 costs.

308 The main problem that may be faced by these installations is the capacity of the DH return line
309 to absorb heat from ST when there are lots of distributed systems connected to them.

310 Although, in actuality, this problem does not exist due to the development situation, in the
311 future it will need to be taken into account to avoid the collapse of the DH network.

312 6 Conclusion & Further work

313 This paper has studied the technical and economic feasibility for the integration of unglazed ST
314 collectors in buildings, and its connection to DH infrastructure.

315 The presented solution relies on the DH in order to balance excess heat production and to
316 supply energy in periods without local production. Overall, DH-connected ST seems to be a
317 promising solution, as it pays back in the most favourable case within ~2 years when compared
318 to traditional heating solutions.

319 With proven performance levels at collector level, and several standalone installations, the
320 adaptation of ST into DH applications needs to be undertaken.

321 This activity will be carried out within the EU h2020 project RELaTED (2017). Within this
322 project, among other activities, an unglazed ST system will be adapted for DH operation, and
323 tested under a controlled test environment in the north of Spain. This same system will be
324 integrated in up to 4 DH networks across Europe.

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